

AFGHANISTAN WATER MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS
AND
IT'S SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS
(A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY DONE IN KABUL)

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**A NARRATIVE ANALYSIS ON AFGHANISTAN WATER
MANAGEMENT AND ITS SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS,
KABUL, AFGHANISTAN**

DECLARATION

I, Zulfiqar Hussaini, hereby declare that this research is my own work and effort and it has not been submitted anywhere for any award. Where other sources of information have been used, they have been acknowledged.

Signature:

Date: ...August, 15, 2019.....

ABSTRACT

This research paper looks at the management issues concerning the water resources and its socio economic impacts in the Afghanistan. The goal is to identify the issues and problems that are affecting the fairness and transparency of the mentioned processes.

After a thorough discussion and analysis done, it has been found out that despite all existed problems, there has been a substantial modification in the creating polices systems for managing water resources of Afghanistan, extend political relations with neighbor countries and prepare agreements, there are external factors affecting the processes in some areas which should be discussed with the related country and solve the problem.

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Executive summary

Water in economic sector of Afghanistan plays a key role from past centuries and even any country is unable to provide facilities for industries, living style and economic development, without managing their water system, as it's a back boon for development of economic, Afghanistan is dried and landlocked country which has experienced many difficulties from dried and less water resources and its highly recommended that from the less water which it has should be used in utmost eligible and efficient method and management.

The total land area of Afghanistan is about 65 million ha of which approximately 80 percent is either mountainous or desert. The forest cover is only 1.3 million ha or about 2 percent of the total land area. In recent years forest cover has reduced due to continuous demands for Fuel wood and illegal logging. The demand for fuel wood by communities is considered less damaging than illegal logging. It is estimated that forest cut rates are exceeding annual growth rates leaving a deficit of about 30,000 ha of forest per year.

Water management is the activity of planning, developing, distributing and optimum use of water resources under defined water policies and regulations. It includes management of water treatment of drinking water, industrial water, sewage or wastewater, management of water resources, management of flood protection, management of irrigation.

Water is a key to strengthening the foundations of Afghanistan's mainly agricultural economy. But only about 5% of the massive international investment and aid in the past decade went to the water sector, and instead the investment occurred only on some small dams and schemes that had no long-term advantage. Water is a contentious resource in Afghanistan; research indicates that disputes over the allocation of water are the second-most commonly cited cause of conflict after land. Afghanistan's irrigation network and water storage capacities have been degraded by decades of war, underinvestment and inadequate management. Water management systems have to tackle three inter-related challenges. Afghanistan water resource has been divided into five water zones, Amu Darya

zone, Harrirod Zone, Murghab Zone, Helmand Zone, Kabul Zone and North Zone which has the capacity of 75 hundred thousand cubic meter water per year which 80% of it is created by fusion of snow and iceboxes where it counted up to 57 hundred thousand cubic meters per year and the rest are underground waters resources. ([Afghanistan studies, Dunya university lecture note, page 22, - 2013](#))

Afghanistan has the capacity of just using 20% of this water for agriculture and sanitation, but unfortunately cause of non-management programs all 80% of this water is wasting or used by neighbor countries like Pakistan and Iran. Although there are some dams in northern and southern provinces for controlling and managing the water but some are not perfect for usage and needs reconstruction or even they are not enough sufficient for controlling all 80% of waters to be not waste or used by the neighbor countries without any reflected positive advantage for Afghanistan, if it uses by Afghanistan.

Lack of agreement on sharing water between Afghanistan and its neighbor countries is a big and sophisticated problem for Afghanistan, while it caused to prevent from creating water management system for irrigation and construction of dams for producing electricity. The security situation is the most huge problem for managing Afghanistan water, it's the most barrier which stops construction of dams and hydropower turbines specially in south and southern areas and provinces such as helmand, nemroz, kunar, Machalgho, and many others areas.

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Chapter-1

Introduction

Water resource management is the activity of planning, developing, distributing and managing the optimum use of water resources.

It is a sub-set of water cycle management which preferably, water resources management planning has regard to all the competing demands for water and seeks to allocate water on an equitable basis to satisfy all uses and demands.

OR;

Water management is the control and movement of water resources to minimize damage to life and property and to maximize efficient beneficial use.

Water management helps us to:

- Reduce the risk of harm due to flooding
- Provide a better system for irrigation
- Use water in a better way to satisfy and all requirement and needs for agriculture.

Water is an essential resource or factors for all life on the earth, as of the research the water resources on earth only three percent of its fresh and tow-third of the freshwater is locked up in ice caps and glaciers and the remaining one percent, a fifth is in remote, in accessible areas and much seasonal rainfall and floods that cannot easily be used.

Much effort in water resource management is directed at optimizing the use of water and in minimizing the environmental impact of water use on the natural environment. The observation of water as an integrated part of the ecosystem is based on integrated water resource management, where the quantity and quantity and quality of the ecosystem help to determine the nature of the natural resources.

Afghanistan

Afghanistan is a mountainous and landlocked country; it is linked with five out of its six neighbor countries through water, as:

- With Tajikistan through Amu river basin
- With Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan through Amu river

- With Turkmenistan and Iran through Harirod- Murghab basin.
- With Iran through Helmand River
- With Pakistan through Kabul river

Water is a key to strengthening the foundations of Afghanistan's mainly agricultural economy. But only about 5% of the massive international investment and aid in the past decade went to the water sector, and instead the investment occurred only on some small dams and schemes that had no long-term advantage.

Climate

Afghanistan is characterized by a continental climate, although the presence of mountains causes many local variations. The typical climate varies from arid in the South and Southwest to semi-arid in most other parts of the country. The high mountain ranges of 3 Hindu Kush and Pamir are moderate humid and covered by permanent snow and glaciers at altitudes above 5,000 m.

With a few exceptions of some locations receiving sufficient rainfall in spring (Northern slopes of Hindu Kush above 1,000m altitude), the climate is not favorable for rain fed agriculture. During winter, temperatures are low and precipitation occurs in form of snow whereas during summer, temperatures are high and rainfall is virtually zero. Without irrigation supplies, these arid to semi-arid areas cannot support any irrigation.

In Afghanistan, the water availability for irrigation purposes is mainly a function of effective rainfall and surface as well as groundwater resources - which depend in turn on the amount and distribution (time and space) of precipitation. Therefore, considering variations in precipitation as the most decisive parameter, Afghanistan can be divided into 6 climatic zones. The general features of these climatic zones are given in Table 2.

Table 2. General features of 6 climatic zones of Afghanistan Zone Name

No	province	Precip. (mm)	Dry (months)	Frost (months)
1	Badakhshan (without Wakhan)	300-800	2-6	1 - 9
2	Central and Northern mountains	200- 600	2-9	0-8
3	3 Eastern and Southern mountains	100-700	2-9	0-10
4	Wakhan corridor and Pamir	<100 - 500	2-5	5-12
5	Turkestan plains	<100 - 400	5-8	0-2
6	Western + South-western Lowlands	<100 - 300	6-12	0-3

In the South-western desert plains, frost can occur in any month of the year even when temperatures reach a daily maximum of up to 40° C. Daily 4 minimum temperatures in the Northern (Turkestan) plains can be as low as -20° C in winter and as high as +50° C in summer at one and the same location.

Water can divide countries and communities but can also bind them together. Managing water resources effectively is critical for Afghanistan's development, security and stability. Addressing its many water problems requires an integrated approach that does the following;

- (1) Reduces competition over scarce water resources through more efficient irrigation systems, drought resistant crops, and public awareness campaigns.
- (2) Increases the supply of water through water harvesting and infrastructure investments.
- (3) Improves water governance by addressing the inequitable access to water for marginalized groups, reducing corruption in the sector, supporting the community management of water, and building capacity for dispute resolution.

- (4) Understands and prepares for the impact of climate and other human-driven change that will impact Afghanistan's water security.
- (5) Improves Trans- boundary water management.

Present situation of water management in Afghanistan

In accordance to the USA survey team in 2009, Afghanistan has the capacity of 75 hundred thousand cubic meter water per year from rainwater and underground waters resources.

Afghanistan has the capacity of just using 20% of this water for agriculture and sanitation, but unfortunately cause of non-management programs all 80% of this water is wasting or used by neighbor countries like Pakistan and Iran. Although there are some dams in northern and southern provinces for controlling and managing the water but some are not perfect for usage and needs reconstruction or even they are not enough sufficient for controlling all 80% of waters to be not waste or used by the neighbor countries without any reflected positive advantage for Afghanistan.

Ministry of energy and water is focusing to construct and reconstruct dams in order to save waters from moving to the neighbor countries or wastes without achieving any benefits from it.

But this program is facing with lots of problems in security aspects and neighbor countries interference, such as Kamal Khan Dam which was going to be reconstruct in to four phases and Ministry of energy and water signed the contract with one of the construction company from Tajikistan, they build up the first phase and by starting the second phase they have faced with problems including though security issues and direct interference of Iran.

Initially the construction work on Kamal Khan Dam has been started in the Charborjak district of southwestern Nimroz province 2009.

This dam was being constructed over the Helmand River, about 95 kilometers from Zaranj city. For construction of this project an agreement signed between Ministry of energy and water and TADES Tajik construction firm on august.

The work included the construction of a 3,400-metre wall having 32 meters width and 6 to 11 meters height which this contract had the cost of \$9,850,000 to be provided by the Ministry of Water and Energy. In the second phase, a similar wall on the other side of the river would be constructed and the river's bed cemented. In the third phase power producing generators would be installed, which calls the last stage to complete the project and nearly 40,000 acres of land would come under irrigation and 8.5megawatts of electricity would be produce with the completion of the project.

Although the concern of Kamal khan dam officially shared through Ministry of Foreign affairs and Energy and water with Iran ambassador in Kabul in order to solve the problem and complete this project.

Beside that Afghan Consulate General in Mashad had informed the Afghan government about concerns expressed by Iranian analysts regarding the dam's construction over the Helmand River in a statement to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs they claim constructing the dam over the Helmand River is against a protocol signed between the two countries.

Kamal Khan Dam was one of the major development projects of Afghanistan. Afghan government is in search of financial sources to fund the third phase of the dam. With the completion of the third phase Afghan government will be able to control Helmand river's water. The Kamal Khan dam consists of three phases.

QUICK FACTS:

- The first phase was completed by a Tajik construction company in 2012, as mentioned before.
- The second phase was completed in 2015.

- The completion of the construction of the second phase was delayed due to lack of funds.
- The dam has the capacity to produce 8.5MW of electricity and to irrigate 80,000 hectares of land.
- The dam is being constructed on the Helmand River in Chahar Burjak district of Nimroz province.
- The construction work on the vital project had begun in 1973 but held in abeyance due to country's security situation.

Why I came to choose this topic?

One of the biggest concerns for water-based resources in the future is the sustainability of the current and even future water resource allocation. As water becomes short, the important issue is to arise on how to manage the water in order to meet the requirement and also finding a balance between what is needed by the humans and what is needed in the environment is also an important issue which we should take steps for achieving the goal for managing the water resources.

We should attempt to create sustainable freshwater systems have been seen on a national level in countries such as Afghanistan, and such commitments to the environment could set a model for the rest of LDCs. The field of water resources management will have to continue to adapt to the current and future issues facing the allocation of water. With the growing uncertainties of global climate changes and the long-term impacts of management actions, the decision-making will be even more difficult. It is important that ongoing climate change will lead to situations that have not been encountered.

Chapter-2

Literature review

A comprehensive assessment of water management done for the past 50 years of water development in using in agriculture sector and evaluation of the benefits, costs and impacts which the communities face today with those challenges.

It is a multi-process and its aim is to assess the current state of knowledge in motivating ideas on how to manage water resources in order to meet the growing needs for agricultural products and humane life needs and to contribute for reducing the poverty and bring food sufficiently to the human life and also contribute the environmental sustainability.

The findings of the written paper indicated that better investment and management decision in water and agriculture in the near future by considering their impact over the next 50 years will develop the economics of a country and will change it into a developed country and bring it out from the list of LDCs.

This assessment was produced by a broad partnership of researchers and policy makers using an assessment process that engaged networks of partners to produce and manufacture knowledge and elaborate innovative methods and responses. And also it is indicated that this assessments is distinct review rather than scientists which is driven by a specific problem rather than more general scientific theories.

The targeted audience of this assessment are the people who make the investment and management decisions in water management for agriculture and agricultural producers, water managers, investors, policy makers and civil society, in addition the assessment should inform the general public about these important issues in order to help them to make better decision through the political processes and social movements.

“Thinking differently about water is essential for achieving our triple goal of ensuring food security, reducing poverty and conserving ecosystems” (*Ramiro Aurin Lopera, water management monograph-Water for life, 2005, Pg:33-35*)

Water for food- water for life

The last 50 years have seen remarkable developments in water resources and in agriculture. Huge developments in hydraulic infrastructure have put water at the service of people, while the world population grew from 2.5 billion in 1950 to 6.5 billion today, the irrigated area doubled and water withdrawals tripled.

Agricultural productivity grew thanks to new crop varieties and fertilizers, fueled by additional irrigation water, world food production outstripped population growth. Global food prices declined markedly and the greater use water for irrigated agriculture-benefited farmers and poor people- propelling economies, improving livelihoods, and fighting hunger.

But much unfinished business remains. In 2003, 850 million people in the world were food insecure 60% of them living in south Asia and Africa and 70% of the poor live in rural areas. In Africa the number of food-insecure people rose from 125 million in 1980 to 200 million in 2000.

The last 50 years have also witnessed unprecedented changes in ecosystems, with many negative consequences. The millennium ecosystem assessment pointed out that growth in agriculture has been responsible for much of this change. Agricultural practices have contributed primarily to the loss of regulating ecosystem service-such as pollination, biological pest control, food retention capacity and changes in microclimate regulation and to the loss of biodiversity and habitats.

New challenges beyond scarcity

Energy affects water management now and will do so even more in the future. Energy prices are rising, pushing up the costs of pumping water, manufacturing fertilizers, and

transporting products. This will have implications for access to water and irrigation. Increase hydropower will mean increased competition for water with agriculture. Climate change policy is increasingly supporting greater reliance on bioenergy as an alternative to fossil fuel-based energy. But this is not consistently coupled with the water discussion. The comprehensive assessment estimates that with heavy reliance on bioenergy the amount of agricultural in 2050 to support increased bioenergy use will be about what is depleted for all of agriculture today.

Trust on bioenergy will further intensify competition for water and land, so awareness of the “double-edged” nature of bioenergy needs to be raised.

Urbanization and the global market will dictate the choices of farmers around the world. Changes in the global market and the spread of globalization will determine the profitability of agriculture. Where suitable infrastructure and national policies are in place, a variety of shifting niche markets will emerge, creating opportunities for innovative entrepreneurial farmers.

In some countries the contribution of farming to the national economy will shrink, with implications for smallholders and subsistence farmers who rely on extension, technology and regional markets. The demographics of farming change with urbanization many women and older people will be left in rural areas to look after farms yet agricultural development remains the single most promising engine of growth in the majority of sub-Saharan countries.

To ensure the sustainability of the agriculture sector in many of these countries, investments in technology and capacity building need to go hand in hand with policies that make farming profitable.

Where is there hope? Increasing the productivity of land and water

Closing the gap in agricultural productivity in many parts of world is some sort of lays hopes, even today there is no greater than the fields of the Roman Empire and in realizing the exexploered potential that lies in better water management along with no

miraculous changes in policy and production techniques. The world has enough fresh water to produce food for all, but leaders must take action before loss of this opportunity of using water.

In addition 75% of the additional food we need over the next decades could be met by bringing the production levels of farmers up to 80% of what farmers get from comparable land, it's better to manage better the water and play key roles in bridging the gap of water scarcest.

Author: David Moldenfor, A Comprehensive Assessment of Water Management, 22883 Quicksilver Drive, Sterling, VA 20166-2012, USA, 2007

Afghanistan and its trans- boundary water management on the AMU Darya:

The Amu Darya River is regionally important. It is the largest river in central Asia (I.e. the five post-soviet republics) and the second largest in the terms of flow in Afghanistan. It is shared by six states, Afghanistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyz republic, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan. It is rises in Afghanistan, the Kyrgyz republic and Tajikistan and the river then flow for 2400 km through these states Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan.

Average annual flow of Amu Darya

Country	Average annual flow (km3)	Withdrawals (km3)
Afghanistan	17.0	5 est
Iran	<3	NA
Kyrgyz republic	1.6	0.15
Tajikistan	49.6	7.9
Turkmenistan	1.5	22
Uzbekistan	5.1	22
Aral sea	-	9.3
Total	79	66.35

Sources: Glantz, 2005; Micklin, 2000; Ahmad & Wasiq, 2003.

The Amu Darya is an equally important asset for Afghanistan. For half of its length, it flows either inside Afghanistan or along its border between 13-40% of Afghanistan's area and more than 255 of its population are within the river basin.

The Amu Darya area is the most agriculturally productive in Afghanistan, containing 1.16 million ha of irrigated land and only 385,000 ha of these are in sub-basins with permanent flow to the Amu Darya however it is worth nothing at this point there are considerable variations in the hydro data on Afghanistan.

Author: (AFGHANISTAN AND TRANSBOUNDARY WATER MANAGEMENT ON THE AMU DARYA: A POLITICAL HISTORY (Glantz, 2005, p 26; Micklin, 2000, p 4, Ahmad & Wasiq, 2003).

Afghanistan water usage and its barriers:

As mentioned before Afghanistan is a dried and landlocked country and the barriers in managing of its less water is divided into the following two parts:

- ✓ Natural barriers, which includes of seasonal problems of un-scheduled rains, herb coverage in water raise zones and rivers, being salty of waters in some areas, location of Afghanistan while its most waters flows in to the neighbor countries.
- ✓ Execution barriers, that includes of ancient system of usage from water resource, censing of water during transferring to the aimed area, creation of dust dams, dried and ruins of canals, and agricultural lands which are not in a single portion to be irrigated in a good and efficient system.

The above two barriers can be an alert for Afghanistan people to enforce and try as much as possible in order to make the system of using water in efficient ways and prevent the waste of waters to the neighbor countries.

Afghanistan lakes:

Lakes can be called to those areas which are depression of some parts in earth which are separate from rivers and fills through rain waters and they are one of the most

important sources of water in Afghanistan, mountainous lakes are commonly feeds from iceboxes and snow fusions and in smooth areas they feeds from rain waters.

The most important lakes in Afghanistan is Zarqool lake in pamir area with 6-10 km length and almost 4 km wide, Chaqmaqchin lake Pamir area with 17 km length and 2.5 km wide, Shiwa lake in Badakhshan province, Mugoos lake in Ghazni province with 13 thousand hectare land , Nawar lake in Ghazni province with 4200 hectare land and this is a salty lake, Band-e-Amer lake in Bameyan Province which is included of five dams, such as Haibat dam, Qanbar dam, Ghulamaan dam, Zulfiqar Dam and Panirak dam.

([Afghanistan studies, Dunya university page 24, year 2013](#))

Natural productive processes

As a part of ecosystem water is to provide a wide range of benefits services while many of those service takes the form of intangible amenity value and also it include of tangible benefits too such as fisheries, wildlife and natural plants that provides useful products and services.

By providing s source of food and water for community, there are lots of ways to help humans to live in a comfort moment of life, While only ten to 15 percent of the total world catch is from fresh water, the freshwater catch constitutes an important source of food in some areas and also we can notify the following operations as well.

- ✓ Agricultural Production
- ✓ Industrial Production
- ✓ Electric Power Production
- ✓ And also water know as a socio-economic development element and
- ✓ psychological welfare

Chapter-3

Research methodology

This research is although not enough for solving the problems of water management in Afghanistan but it may help in somehow at least to have an idea for creating policy and system for managing water in Afghanistan and benefit from it in agriculture sector and producing energy for daily usage of people, in order to bring out Afghanistan from almost 95% importer stage specially in field of food and cereal and also change the systems of energy from purchasing in high cost from neighbor countries like Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan instead we could produce enough energy of electricity through a good management in water sector.

So this research has done through primary data and secondary data, that means this research is done based on previous topics and papers written regarding Afghanistan water management and also a set of questions made by myself to ask people in different area and different task environment in order to have ideas and point of view related to this topic.

3.1- Data Collection

3.1.1- Primary

All information will be collected directly on the issues related to the Afghanistan water management. The information collected will be completely gathered within the Ministry of energy and water and also from the topics related to water management.

3.1.1.1 Questionnaire

A comprehensive questionnaire designed to be from different individuals in different areas and positions in order to gather required information.

On a sample wise some heads of departments and heads of units will be targeted for collecting necessary information on random basis.

The questionnaire will mainly contain specific questions related to the water management and its socio-economic effects along with some general questions. The questionnaire in total will have 14 numbers of questions within multiple choice arenas.

3.1. Analysis Plan

There will be a comprehensive analysis on the problems statement and problem questions, all the causes, issues, influences, interventions, limitations, lack of policy and its implementation and etc. to see where the problem lives in. the analysis will be done in two following methods.

3.1.1 Quantitative

There will be a statistical analysis done based on the available data in the recruitment unit of HR department and find out how, where and to what extent are the discrepancies.

3.1.2 Qualitative

Overall research will be qualitative and analytical. The analysis will be on the basis of fact and evidences and interviews.

All the facts and evidences will be collected and an analysis will be done to find out the center of each problem.

3.2 Limitations

There will be many limitations in terms of data collection and finding of facts and evidences, some of the major ones that may limit the area of my research are listed below:

- Non skilled people
- Not allowing to have interview and asked them questions;
- Limitation on giving accurate information as considered their confidence policy
- Lack of coordination and many more.

Problem statements:

- 1- There are no Water-sharing agreements between Afghanistan and its neighbor countries.

Lack of agreement on sharing water between Afghanistan and its neighbor countries is a big and sophisticated problem for Afghanistan, while it caused to prevent from creating water management system for irrigation and construction of dams for producing electricity.

Up to date, there is no any agreement to be signed between Afghanistan and its neighbor countries but only one agreement of water sharing signed with Iran on Helmand River during Raza Shah Pahlavi's regime.

This may cause many challenges and create problems for not using water for irrigation, agriculture and producing power on the time while Afghanistan has the utmost necessary for these sectors and its all because of non-agreement of water sharing.

Let's example the problem of non-agreement water sharing between Iran and Afghanistan on Harriod-Murghab river:

- Iran analyst claims that increase in consumption of water in Afghanistan, negatively affects water supply to Iran.
- Iran perceives the construction of hydroelectric dams on the afghan side of the basins as a direct security threat for itself.
- In addition to political tensions, Iranian analyst claims that, increasing human strain on the Sistan wetlands due to mass migrations is unsustainable and may lead to a major environmental disaster.

If Iran, Afghanistan and Pakistan sign contracts on water sharing, that will become the source of cooperation between them instead of source of conflict.

2- Unsecure situation is a big barrier for water management in Afghanistan.

The security situation is the most huge problem for managing Afghanistan water, it's the most barrier which stops construction of dams and hydropower turbines specially in south and southern areas and provinces such as helmand, nemroz, kunar, Machalgho, and many others areas.

Due to this unstable situation, the construction companies are not courage to attend on obtaining such kind of projects because there is no guarantee of their investment and

there life. Either they are suffering from burning their machineries or being kidnapped by terrorists who are having almost the leadership of those areas.

Questions:

- 1- What are the options and its consequences for improving water productivity in agriculture?
- 2- What are the land and water degradation on water productivity and on water management systems?
- 3- How we could build-up a system that could work better to manage water in Afghanistan?
- 4- What is the benefit of managing water and what are its socio-economic impacts?
- 5- How to make a good relationship with neighbor countries for solving issues related to the water?

Chapter-4

Analysis

I made analysis on information collected as quantitative data based on questionnaire including 14 questions related to water management system and its importance factors and affects and asked from 42 different answerers who are self-employee, employed in public and private sectors and also from students of distinct colleges including common people which the information is written below as started into:

Part # 1

Part number one of my questionnaire is consist of personal information of the answerer which is cleared to be asked regarding age, marital status, educational qualification, these personal information is just help the paper to be viewed from different type of ideas from single and married, from undergraduate up to master degree, cause the ideas which give by the answerer would be different as their educational qualification, their age and their live stage.

1- Age:

The people who answered the questions were 8 people from age 20-25, and 12 people from age 26-30, and people from age 31-35 and from age 36-40, their point of view regarding the factors and effect of water management in Afghanistan was differs from each other and related individually to every of them which the writer did have any advice or recommendation in giving the answer or taking the view of the answerer.

Age Range	Participants	Gender	Percentage	Participants
20 – 25	7	Male & Female	Male	42
26 – 30	14		95%	
31 – 35	16		Female	
36 – 40	5		5%	

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

2- Gender:

The answerer included of ninety percent (95%) were male and five percent (5%) were female, in this questionnaire the point of view and ideas are collected from both and there was no any confusion, recommendation or suggestion made by the writer to make the answerer to respond according to his choice and there were no any conflict of interest.

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

3- Qualification:

As mentioned before I made this questionnaire from distinct type of people such as graduate, post graduate, under graduate, master and phd, so here from all answerer 25 people were graduated with educational qualification of bachelor, 8 people were in master position and the remain 9 of them were undergraduate.

Qualification	Participants	Job	Participants
Under graduate	9	Employment	33
Graduate	25		
Post graduate	8	Un-Employment	9

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

4- Marital Statues

In this section I considered the marital status of the answerers, because the single people point of view in accordance to the socio economic prospective is different with the ideas and view of the married people, so from these 42 people the answerer 25 people were married, 7 people were engaged and the remaining 10 people were single.

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Part # 2

The part number two of my questionnaire is consist of multiple choice question, where I brought out the sub-questions from the main question of problem statement in order to find out answers from people to be counted as a support information and find the solution ways for problems.

Questions made as below and answers were directly without any changes translated herein:

Questions:

1- What does water management means?

The answers for the above question was answered by the writer as

- a. Controlling water
- b. managing water resources to minimize damages
- c. maximize efficient beneficial use
- d. both b and c is

From these 42 people 5 % percent selected **A** (controlling water), 33% percent answered by selecting **B** (managing water resources to minimize damages), 10% selected **C** (maximize efficient beneficial use) and the remained 52% selected **D** (both b and c is).

Answers	A	B	C	D
Participants	13	2	4	21

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

From the above information and ideas selected and given through answerer and matching it with the definition of water manages as defined (water management is the activity of planning, developing, distributing and optimum use of water resource under water policies and regulations) of it seems that water management purpose in accordance to the ideas of the answerer and definition is refers to the preparation of plans for managing water resource, for distribution of water in accordance to the water management policies, and optimizing the output of achieving benefits from managing water resource.

2- How agree you are that water management can effect socio-economic of Afghanistan?

This question was elaborated as to select:

- a. Strongly agree
- b. Agree
- c. Disagree
- d. Strongly disagree

The answer which I received from answerer was 91% selected A and 9% selected b, it seems that water management in Afghanistan is a factor which has a strong direct effect on socio-economic system while it brings changes in industrial sector, increase agriculture outputs and creates employment and generate hydropower for better development.

Answers	A	B	C	D
Participants	38	4	0	0

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

3- The main challenge for Afghanistan water management is?

- a. Being landlocked b. Regional insecurity c. lack of specialists

The answer received is, 72% is b (regional insecurity), 23% is c (lack of specialists) and only 5% is a (being landlocked), the answers indicates that the most barrier for Afghanistan water management is the security problem while it continuous from 35 years and damaged all systems including water resource management and still it's an enormous stoppage for implementation of projects in water management sector.

Answers	A	B	C	D
Participants	2	30	10	0

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

4- What is the future of Afghanistan through its agriculture?

- a. Top agricultural zone b. industrialized country c. self-sufficient

The answers received from people consist of 13% agreed with a (top agricultural zone), 79% agreed with b (industrialized country) and 8% agreed with c (self-sufficient).

To the view of people and papers written by economist, the effect of agriculture in revelation of industrial sector has straight and most positive as it can be counted as an economic support for being industrialized country while it prepares the raw materials for production sector of industry and as well it may full fill the needs of necessity of living.

Answers	A	B	C	D
Participants	5	33	4	0

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

5- How we categorize the water resource of Afghanistan?

- a. Main agricultural resources
- b. live resource
- c. living initial resource

For this question the answer received was: 75% is selected A (main agricultural resource), 2% is selected b (live resource) and 23% selected c (living initial resource).

If we discuss through this question its clear that by water management we can contribute agriculture at its utmost level while we distribute water within a proper plan to prevent misuse and wastes, and also prepare plans of irrigations for agricultural lands which cause to increase level of agricultural outputs.

Answers	A	B	C	D
Participants	31	1	10	0

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

6- What factors doe's water management brings?

- a. Reduce misuse of water
- b. meet all irrigation requirement
- c. increase water supply
- d. all three factors

In this question the answerer were agreed 1% with a (reduce misuse of water), 7% b (meet all irrigation requirement), 3% c (increase water supply) and 89% d (all three factors).

The answers goes to the ideas where water management may cause to meet all irrigation requirement, increase water supply system, reduce misuse of water from wasting and also create a system for water distribution in order to meet agricultural and irrigation system.

Answers	A	B	C	D
Participants	1	3	1	37

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

7- How to solve problems of water sharing with neighbor countries?

- a. Establishing political relations
- b. assurance of water suppliers
- c. extend foreign relations
- d. signing water sharing agreement

The answer received for this question were 25% agreed with a (establishing political relations), 0% (agreed with assurance of water suppliers), 18% agreed with c (extend foreign relations) and 57% agreed with d (singing water sharing agreement).

To analysis the answers we can consider to be established political relations and extend foreign relations, but the singing contracts on water sharing is a most important which will be a well-known document by united nation and both countries.

Answers	A	B	C	D
Participants	10	0	8	24

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

8- Thinking differently about water is essential for?

- a. Conserving ecosystems
- b. ensuring of food and security
- C. reducing poverty
- d. achieving all triple goals

By receiving answer for above question it realized to be agreed on 25% a (conserving ecosystems), 0% b (ensuring of food and security), 20% c (reducing poverty) and 55% d (achieving all triple goals)

Answers	A	B	C	D
Participants	10	0	8	24

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

9- How to control trans-boundary waters?

- a. Establishing canal
- b. establish hydrology system
- C. creating political relations
- d. all three categories

Answers received as 2% a (establishing canal), 12% b (establish hydrology system), 20% c (creating political relations) and 66% for d (all three categories).

Answers	A	B	C	D
Participants	1	5	8	28

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

10- Why water management is important?

- a. Agriculture improvement
- b. economic support
- c. move toward industrialization
- d. all is right

The answers for the above question is achieved as 25% for a (agriculture improvement), 12% for b (economic support), 18% for C (move toward industrialization) and 45% for D (all is right)

Answers	A	B	C	D
Participants	10	5	8	19

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

11-What are the main causes of water system mismanagement in Afghanistan?

- a. Lack of proper management
- b. not having enough water
- C. insecure situation
- d. a and b is correct

The answer is 35% for a (lack of proper management), 2% for C (bot having enough water), 20% for B (insecure situation) and 43% for D (a and b is correct).

Answers	A	B	C	D
Participants	15	8	1	18

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

12-How to facilitate our agricultural sector through water distribution?

- a. Thorough proper irrigation and water distribution
- b. Helping the farmers by machineries
- c. Creating training programs for cultivation
- d. Purchasing seed

The answers are commonly laid on 64% for a (through a proper irrigation and water distribution system), 11% for b (helping the farmers by machineries), 8% for C (creating training programs for cultivation) and 17% for d (purchasing seed).

Answers	A	B	C	D
Participants	27	5	3	17

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

13-How is possible to reduce poverty through water management?

- a. Improving agriculture outputs
- b. Establish hydropower energy to support industries
- c. Giving money
- d. Both a and b is correct

The answers are commonly laid on 10% for a (improving agriculture outputs), 40% for b (establishing hydropower energy to support industries), 2% for C (giving money) and 48% for d (both a and b is correct).

Answers	A	B	C	D
Participants	4	17	1	20

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

14-What are the outcomes of better water management?

- a. Industrialized country
- b. stable agriculture systems
- c. generation of enough hydropower
- d. all three categories

The answers are commonly laid on 7% for a (industrialized country), 22% for b (stable agriculture systems), 24% for C (generation of enough hydropower) and 49% for d (all three categories).

Answers	A	B	C	D
Participants	4	17	1	20

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Source: Zulfiqar Hussaini

Chapter -5

Conclusion

As discussed, Afghanistan although is a landlocked country but it has that much water to fulfill its agricultural needs, use it for generating hydropower and help the industrialization sector to be moved into self-sufficient.

We mentioned that Afghanistan water is divided into the types of canals, karez, sarband, waters from snow, underground water, iceboxes and some dams, these waters cause to have some trans-boundary waters which are shared with neighbor countries which are bounded by Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Pakistan and Iran.

These trans-boundary waters creates political problems for Afghanistan specially by Pakistan and Iran, from Harirod and Kabul river, these conflicts does not permit Afghanistan to build up the dams on the rivers and use it in order to full facilitate the agriculture sector which can be considered the main source of income for almost 80% of people in Afghanistan, and for generation and establishment of hydropower systems to stop purchasing power from outside countries and to be the top help for industrial sector to assist the industrialism for extension and increase level of employment.

In accordance to the people point of view water management has positive effects on socio-economic of Afghanistan through its power generation and enough support to agriculture system in order to have a best enough irrigation system and hydropower stations for generating power for industries and daily usage of people.

Water management reduces misuse of water; establish stable irrigation system, increase water supply and use as a main agricultural resource. Essentially water management cause to conserve ecosystems, ensure enough food and help security, while through establishment of industries sector level of employment is increases and reduce poverty from society. It helps Afghanistan to be an industrialized country in the future if the management has long term plans by the help of establishes political relations with neighbor countries, generate hydropower system, prepare enough accurate policies for better irrigation, signing contracts on water sharing with Iran and Pakistan, and extend foreign relationship.

Water is a contentious resource in Afghanistan; research indicates that disputes over the allocation of water are the second-most commonly cited cause of conflict after land. Afghanistan's irrigation network and water storage capacities have been degraded by decades of war, underinvestment and inadequate management. Water management systems have to tackle three inter-related challenges.

The first is to manage the increased demand for water: Population growth and economic development are rapidly increasing the demand for water. The second challenge is to reduce the risk of climate-related disasters: Droughts and floods are a feature of life in Afghanistan. Water can divide countries and communities but can also bind them together. Managing water resources effectively is critical for Afghanistan's development, security and stability.

Research implication

A student can use this research as a reference to know the way of research, if her or she studies deeply he or she will be able to start its own thesis and well analyze easily the method of preparing papers including all questionnaire and problems statements.

All is clearly done in this research and hope to help anyone who may use it as reference.

Managerial Implication:

It cannot be say that this paper is enough accurate and it most reliable and the only reference regarding Afghanistan water management, but it can be a mini help for those managers, leaders, entrepreneur, irrigation engineers and irrigation college students for searching information and use it as a source.

This paper assist them toward having information easily rather than searching the webs and other huge references books and topics, because this paper is tried to be written short enough and to be useful for college students.

Findings:

Water is an essential resource or factor for all life on the earth and its management is an important responsibility in order to reduce the risk of harm due to flooding and provide a better system for irrigation beside that use water in a better way to satisfy all requirements and needs for agriculture, hydropower and drinking water.

But unfortunately due do mismanagement in Ministry of Energy and Water our country water resources are wasting and we are only able to use 20% of 57 hundred thousand cubic meter of water every year which our country has the capacity of production.

Through establishment a stable system for managing water, Afghanistan would be self-sufficient from energy of power through establishing dams and construction of hydropower stations, would be self-sufficient from purchasing food from neighbor countries through development agriculture and systematic irrigation.

Recommendations:

As the water is a domestic commodity it has the most fundamental role of water in socio-economic development so its highly recommended to have its control and provide best management for establishment of canals, dams and irrigation system through-out hydropower generation is another factor of economic development of a country, thus, Afghanistan is a leased development country and does not have any management of its water so in accordance to the information Afghanistan has only the capacity of 25% usage of its water but the rest is wasting or goes to the neighbor countries without any advantage.

Through above facts, its recommended first of all Afghanistan should sign water sharing agreement with Pakistan and Iran in order to build up the dams on Harrirod, Helmand and Kunar rivers, beside agreements the establishment of dams should be started in order to gather waters for better and enough agricultural irrigation and improve the agriculture sector while it helps the country to full fill its essential food necessity of the community and released from being relied on purchasing the primary food necessities from other countries.

The establishment of hydropower systems is the other recommendable factor which helps Afghanistan to ensure of generating enough energy for its population daily usage and industries which make the country self-sufficient to produce its requirement products and change the country from the least developed country in to a developed country.

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Appendices:

This questionnaire is prepared for collecting information in accordance to the points of different view which people have regarding water management of Afghanistan and its socio-economic affects.

Questions are raised as sub-questions but on the basis of main questions related to the questioner which helps to find out some answers for problem statements mentioned on the paper. These questions are asking from different category of people in the society which includes water management specialists, irrigation engineers, students of engineering faculty of Kabul mainly in irrigation sector, employees of ministry of water and energy and common people.

The questionnaire is designed in 4 parts as below. I am requesting to please answer by ticking the correct answer according to your choice and submit back the questionnaire to the researcher.

Your contribution in this research paper will be highly appreciated and this will be considering a help to the academic family of Afghanistan.

Part One personal information of answerer:

Your Name:

Designation:

Employer:

Age: 20-25 26-30 31-35 36-40

Gender: Male Female

Qualification: Under-Graduate Graduate Post-Graduate Doctorate

Marital status: Single Engaged Married In-Relation

Job: Employment Um-Employment

Part Two multiple- choice question:

THESIS QUESTIONNAIRE

This questionnaire is prepared for collecting information in accordance to the points of different view which people have regarding water management of Afghanistan and its socio-economic affects.

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The questionnaire is designed in 4 parts as below. I am requesting to please answer by ticking the correct answer according to your choice and submit back the questionnaire to the researcher.

Your contribution in this research paper will be highly appreciated and this will be considering a help to the academic family of Afghanistan.

Part One personal information of answerer:

Your Name: Mohammad Waheed

Designation: Ahmadzai

Employer: Hakan Agro DMCC

Age: 20-25 26-30 31-35 36-40

Gender: Male Female

Qualification: Under-Graduate Graduate Post-Graduate Doctorate

Marital status: Single Engaged Married In-Relation

Job: Employment Um-Employment

Part Two multiple- choice question:

1. What does water management means?

- a. Controlling water maximize efficient beneficial use b. managing water resource to minimize damages c. both b and c

2. How agree you are that water management can affect socio-economic of Afghanistan?
 Strongly Agree Agree Dis-agree strongly dis-agree
3. The main challenge for Afghanistan water management is?
 Being landlocked Regional insecurity Lack of specialists
4. What is the future of Afghanistan through its agriculture?
 Top Agricultural zone industrialized country self -sufficient
5. How we categorize the water resource of Afghanistan?
 Main agricultural resources live resource living initial resource
6. What factors doe's water management brings?
 Reduce misuse of water meet all irrigation requirement
 increase water supply all three factors
7. How to solve problems of water sharing with neighbor countries?
 Establishing political relations Assurance of water suppliers extend foreign relations
 signing water sharing agreement
8. Thinking differently about water is essential for?
 Conserving ecosystems ensuring of food and security
 reducing poverty achieving all triple goals
9. How to control trans-boundary waters?
 Establishing canal establish hydrology system
 Creating political relations all three categories
10. Why water management is important?
 Agriculture improvement Economic support
 Move toward industrialization All is right

11. What are the main causes of water system mismanagement in Afghanistan?

- a. Lack of proper management c. Not having enough water
b. Insecure situation d. a and b is correct ✓

12. How to facilitate our agricultural sector through water management?

Through a proper irrigation and water distribution ✓

Helping the farmers by machineries

Creating training programs for cultivation purchasing seeds

13. How is possible to reduce poverty through water management?

- a. Improving agriculture outputs c. giving money
b. Establish hydropower energy to support industries d. both a and b is correct ✓

14. What are the outcomes of better water management?

Industrialized country stable agriculture system

Generation of enough hydropower All three categories ✓

THESIS QUESTIONNAIRE

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Your contribution in this research paper will be highly appreciated and this will be considering a help to the academic family of Afghanistan.

Part One personal information of answerer:

Your Name: *Hafeezullah Sabarwall*

Designation: *Finance officer*

Employer: *MOF*

Age: 20-25 26-30 31-35 36-40

Gender: Male Female

Qualification: Under-Graduate Graduate Post-Graduate Doctorate

Marital status: Single Engaged Married In-Relation

Job: Employment Um-Employment

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